

The Relationship between UK GDP and Consumer Price Inflation

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1. Introduction

Consumer Price Inflation (CPI), a measure of inflation and prices, is the change in prices of a basket of goods and services over time (OECD 2023). Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on the other hand, measures the monetary value of finished goods and services produced by a country over time (Callen 2023). This paper examines the statistical relationship between UK GDP growth and UK consumer price inflation from the first quarter of 2003 to the first quarter of 2023. The UK Office for National Statistics, through Kaggle datasets, provides quarterly data on GDP growth and inflation throughout this period. The objective of the study is to evaluate the data on these two important economic metrics and establish whether there exists a relationship between GDP growth and CPI in the UK. Understanding the relationship between economic growth and inflation offers crucial insights or information about the state of macroeconomics in the United Kingdom.

1.1 Research Questions

- i. What are the descriptive statistics, distribution, and trend of the UK GDP growth between 2003 and 2023?
- ii. What are the statistical descriptions, distribution, and trends of the UK CPI for the same period?
- iii. Is there a statistically significant relationship between UK GDP growth and CPI between 2003 and 2023? If yes, what is the strength and direction of the correlation?

1.2 Data Collection

To answer these questions, quarterly time series data on UK GDP growth and inflation from Q1 2003 to Q1 2023 were obtained from the Office for National Statistics database, which was accessible in Kaggle datasets.

UK GDP Growth % (2003 - 2023)

Date	UK GDP (%)
2003 Q1	0.6
2003 Q2	0.9
2003 Q3	1.0
2003 Q4	0.8
2004 Q1	0.4
2004 Q2	0.5
2004 Q3	0.2
2004 Q4	0.3
2005 Q1	0.8

2005	0.9
Q2	
2005	0.9
Q3	
2005	1.0
Q4	
2006	0.3
Q1	
2006	0.2
Q2	
2006	0.1
Q3	
2006	0.4
Q4	
2007	1.0
Q1	
2007	0.7
Q2	
2007	0.8
Q3	
2007	0.7
Q4	

2008	0.5
Q1	
2008	-0.5
Q2	
2008	-1.5
Q3	

Table 1: UK GDP Growth (%) (2003 - 2023)

Source: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/matarrgaye/uk-gross-domestic-product-quarterly-1955-2023?select=series-120623.xls>

UK Consumer Prices Inflation (%) (2003 - 2023)

Date	UK Consumer Price Inflation (%)
2003	1.5
Q1	
2003	1.3
Q2	
2003	1.4
Q3	
2003	1.3
Q4	

2004		1.3
Q1		
2004		1.3
Q2		
2004		1.3
Q3		
2004		1.5
Q4		
2005		1.8
Q1		
2005		1.9
Q2		
2005		2.4
Q3		
2005		2.2
Q4		
2006		2.1
Q1		
2006		2.4
Q2		
2006		2.5
Q3		

2006	2.7
Q4	
2007	2.8
Q1	
2007	2.6
Q2	
2007	2.0
Q3	
2007	2.3
Q4	
2008	2.5
Q1	
2008	3.3
Q2	
2008	4.5
Q3	

Table 2: UK Consumer Prices Inflation (%)

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/matarrgaye/uk-consumer-price-inflation-quarterly-and-annual?select=series-100623.xls>

The data provided is very relevant to the study and the research questions since it offers the UK GDP Growth (%) and Consumer price inflation (%) from 2003 to 2023, which will be straightforward to compare, contrast, and correlate.

The data was then analyzed in Microsoft Excel to generate descriptive statistics, graphs, and charts, as well as conduct regression and correlation analysis. The methodology for this analysis is presented in the following section. The statistical results are subsequently presented and analyzed to conclude the study problems.

3. Methodology

This section outlines the techniques and procedures used in this study to evaluate the relationship between GDP growth and consumer price inflation in the UK during 20 years, from 2003 to 2023. For both datasets, descriptive statistics such as mean, mode, median, range, standard deviation, first quartile (Q1), third quartile (Q3), and interquartile range (IQR) were calculated using Microsoft Excel. These figures reflect each dataset's central tendency as well as spread.

Correlation analysis was used to investigate the statistical relationship between UK GDP growth and inflation rates. The correlation coefficient (r) shows the strength of the linear relationship between parameters, with values ranging from -1 to 1. The coefficient of determination (r^2) shows how much of one variable's variance can be explained by another. In this case, r^2 will show the proportion of variance in inflation that can be explained by GDP.

Regression analysis was conducted to fit a linear regression line that estimated inflation (%) from GDP growth (%). The slope and intercept values (model coefficients) of this line were interpreted. Residual plots were examined to determine whether a linear model was effective for this analysis. On graph generation, histograms were used to visualize data distribution, box plots to identify outliers, and time series plots to analyze patterns, also known as trends, over time.

4. Graphical Representation

Over the last two decades, say from Q1 2003 to Q1 2023, the UK GDP growth has been affected by several factors including trade dynamics, global financial crises, and domestic policy

decisions. The global financial crisis of 2008-2009 was one of the major incidents that influenced GDP growth in the United Kingdom. According to Arioli et al. (2017), the global financial crisis had an enormous effect on the UK's economic performance, with GDP falling by nearly 6.5% between 2008 Q1 and 2009 Q2. This crisis was heightened by the subprime mortgage chaos that occurred in the United States. The UK faced one of the worst recessions in the recent past. In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic caused the UK GDP to drop by approximately 19% then bounced back by close to 17% after the lockdown. The line graph below shows the GDP growth trend over the last 20 years.

Additionally, several variables have affected consumer price inflation in the United Kingdom. According to the Office for National Statistics (2023), energy and fuel price fluctuations have been a major driver of inflation, with greater inflation rates happening during

recessions and oil/energy price spikes in 2008-2009, 2011, and 2022-2023. The graph below shows the UK inflation trend over the last 20 years.

The COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine conflict also tremendously affected the global supply chains, leading to shortfalls of goods and services, which in turn has led to an upsurge in CPI in recent years, most notably from 2021 to 2022, when inflation jumped from about 1% to 9.4%.

5. Mathematical Investigation

To calculate the average for the two variables, separately sum all the values in each column and divide by the total number of observations, in this case 81.

By using Excel, the following are the key descriptive statistics calculated for the quarterly UK GDP growth and consumer price inflation datasets from 2003 to 2023:

<i>UK GDP (%)</i>		<i>UK Consumer Price Inflation (%)</i>	

Mean	0.374074074	Mean	2.437037037
Standard Error	0.35070378	Standard Error	0.194741396
Median	0.5	Median	2.2
Mode	0.6	Mode	2.4
Standard Deviation	3.15633402	Standard Deviation	1.752672562
Sample Variance	9.962444444	Sample Variance	3.071861111
Kurtosis	34.84280529	Kurtosis	6.763322065
Skewness	- 2.169085779	Skewness	2.388180506
Range	37.6	Range	9.1
Minimum	-21	Minimum	0.3
Maximum	16.6	Maximum	9.4
Sum	30.3	Sum	197.4
Count	81	Count	81

The mean quarterly GDP growth rate in the UK was 0.37% throughout the 81 quarters from 2003 to 2023. However, the median of 0.5% is higher than the mean, indicating that the distribution is skewed left, with more low GDP growth quarters as shown in the histogram and box plot below. The enormous standard deviation of 3.16% demonstrates a high volatility in GDP growth.

The kurtosis of 34.8 indicates a distribution that is significantly more peaked than a normal distribution. This corresponds to a time series with periodic substantial GDP changes. The skewness of -2.17 suggests that the data is asymmetrically distributed, with a large left tail of low or negative GDP growth rates, shown in the figure below.

The descriptive statistics demonstrate that UK GDP growth during this period varied significantly from quarter to quarter.

The average UK inflation rate of 2.44% implies that prices are rising considerably on average as shown in the box plot below.

The median and mode are close to the mean, indicating a generally symmetric distribution as indicated in the histogram below. The standard deviation of 1.75% reflects a more modest dispersion of inflation than GDP growth.

Overall, the average for inflation of 2.44% is higher than that of GDP growth of 0.37%. During this period, UK CPI inflation averaged roughly 2.06 percentage points more than GDP growth. The significantly lower average GDP growth depicts the underlying volatility in actual economic activity, which increases and contracts across the business cycle. GDP growth averaged close to zero as quarters of economic expansion were countered by periods of recession and contraction.

The kurtosis of 6.76 suggests that the distribution is slightly peaked than normal. The positive skewness of 2.39 is consistent with the asymmetric right tail of higher inflation rates. Overall, inflation is substantially less volatile than GDP growth over this period. The spread of inflation is limited to a relatively narrow band from quarter to quarter. Also, it is important to note that neither of the box plots has an outlier. This implies that the whole data under investigation fits within their respective ranges. That is to say, no data is found above the maximum values or below the minimum values.

Correlation

	<i>UK GDP</i>	<i>UK Consumer Price</i>
	<i>(%)</i>	<i>Inflation (%)</i>
UK GDP (%)	1	
UK Consumer Price	-	
Inflation (%)	0.025831934	1

A correlation analysis between quarterly UK GDP growth and inflation yields the following:

Correlation coefficient (r) = -0.025831934

The values of r show a weak negative association between the two variables.

Regression

SUMMARY

OUTPUT

Regression Statistics

Multiple R 0.025832

R

R Square 0.000667

Adjusted R Square -0.01198

R Square

Standard Error 1.763142

Error

Observations 81

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
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Regression	1	0.1639	0.1639	0.0527	0.818937			
n		85	85	51				
Residual	79	245.58	3.1086					
		49	7					
Total	80	245.74						
		89						
		<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>
								<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	2.442403	0.197293	12.37959	3.47E-20	2.049701	2.835104	2.049701	2.835104
UK GDP (%)	-0.01434	0.062454	-0.22968	0.818937	-0.13866	0.109967	-0.13866	0.109967

The regression output shows the behaviour of inflation concerning GDP growth. A coefficient of -0.01434 indicates that for every 1% change in GDP, inflation changes by -0.01434%.

Time Series

6. Analysis and Interpretation

The regression line represents the estimated average relationship between the two variables. The negative slope indicates that higher GDP growth correlates with lower inflation on average. In terms of strength, the gently sloping regression line portrays a weak correlation

between the two variables. This is also evident by the nearness of the correlation coefficient (-0.026) to 0.

From the above scatter plot, the linear regression equation estimating inflation change from GDP growth is:

$$\text{Predicted CPI} = 2.4424 - 0.0143 * \text{GDP Growth}$$

The slope of -0.0143 implies that for every 1% point increase in GDP growth, inflation decreases by -0.0143% points. The intercept of 2.4424% represents the estimated inflation baseline level when GDP growth is zero. The regression line fits the data moderately well, explaining 0.07% of the variation in inflation based on GDP growth. The standard error of the regression is 1.76%.

Residual analysis shows no systematic patterns, indicating linear regression is appropriate. The variability of inflation around the regression line reflects the many other factors (macroeconomic indicators) that influence it beyond just GDP growth.

The negative correlation coefficient indicates a weak negative linear relationship between GDP growth and inflation. As GDP growth increases, inflation tends to slightly decrease. This a good measure since, in the real world economy, usually when the GDP of a country rises, the inflation rate decreases.

For the coefficient of determination, the low r^2 value implies that only 0.07% of the variation in consumer price inflation is explained by changes in GDP growth. This suggests that inflation is also affected or rather influenced by many other factors. They include fuel prices, Strong global demand for consumer goods, and supply chain disruption among others (Francis-Devine et al. 2023).

The time series plot of UK GDP growth shows significant volatility from 2003 to 2023. GDP swings from quarter to quarter, with some recessions noticeable as extended spells of negative growth. The lowest points were reached during the 2008-2009 global financial crisis and the 2020 COVID pandemic, which induced a recession. Aside from contractions, growth slowed significantly during the 2011-2012 Eurozone crisis era (Benczes and Szent-Ivanyi 2015).

Short phases of expansion are seen in 2004-2006 and 2010, with consecutive quarters of positive GDP growth exceeding 1%. Overall, the time series captures the cyclical nature of the UK economy over the past two decades. On the other hand, the time series graph below shows that in

the last two decades, the UK registered the lowest inflation of 0.3 in 2015 due to the low cost of food and motor fuels (www.ons.gov.uk, n.d.).

On the other hand, the UK experienced a rapid positive change in inflation percentage i.e. from about 1% in 2021 to 9.4% in 2022 mainly because of high prices of food and energy as a result of the Russia-Ukraine conflict, which cut the supply of goods to UK (Francis-Devine et al. 2023).

Future Prediction

The graph below shows the UK GDP growth forecast from 2010-2028 using the 2003-2023 UK GDP data. A decrease in GDP growth (%) is expected for the next five years, i.e. from 2023 to 2028. These future predictions differ from OECD.org's economic outlook (2023), which shows that the UK GDP will grow by 0.7% in 2024 and 1.2% in 2025.

For inflation, the graph below shows inflation predictions from 2010 to 2028 using the 2003-2023 quarterly consumer prices inflation data.

The general trend in the graph shows that UK inflation will gradually go up for the next five years. According to Michael (2024), inflation in the UK is still expected to sit above the government's target (2%) in 2024 due to damaging economic conditions.

Based on the two forecasted graphs, the researcher cannot rely on the results shown due to limited variables. To improve the forecasts, one should use more advanced techniques such as machine learning algorithms, which include Decision Trees, Random Forests, and XGBOOST Gradient Machine.

7. Conclusion

This report investigated the statistical relationship between UK GDP growth and consumer price inflation from 2003 to 2023. The investigation revealed that GDP growth over this era was highly volatile, with a mean of 0.37%. Inflation remained more constant, averaging 2.44%. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression modeling, and time series charts. The small negative correlation of -0.026 between GDP growth and inflation was unexpected, given that economic theory predicts a positive association. However,

the near-zero correlation suggests that GDP growth has a minor linear relationship with inflation based on this dataset.

The regression model revealed a slightly negative slope, indicating a 0.0143% fall in inflation for every 1% increase in GDP growth. However, the model explained only little of the variation in inflation. The time series charts contrasted the higher frequency variations in GDP with the more consistent inflationary trends. In conclusion, while increased GDP growth frequently leads to some inflationary pressure, many other stronger macroeconomic factors have a significant impact on UK consumer prices. GDP-based models appear insufficient to explain inflation trends. To further understand the factors that contribute to inflation, further research with more macroeconomic variables and sophisticated time series techniques is advised. Instead of depending solely on GDP estimates, monetary policy may necessitate a more comprehensive approach that takes into account a variety of variables.

8. References

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9. Appendices

8.1 Sample of the Dataset

8.2 Excel Screen Shots

Date	UK GDP (%)	UK Consumer Price Inflation (%)
2003 Q1	0.6	1.5
2003 Q2	0.9	1.3
2003 Q3	1.0	1.4
2003 Q4	0.8	1.3
2004 Q1	0.4	1.3
2004 Q2	0.5	1.3
2004 Q3	0.2	1.3
2004 Q4	0.3	1.5

2005	0.8	1.8
Q1		
2005	0.9	1.9
Q2		
2005	0.9	2.4
Q3		
2005	1.0	2.2
Q4		
2006	0.3	2.1
Q1		
2006	0.2	2.4
Q2		
2006	0.1	2.5
Q3		
2006	0.4	2.7
Q4		
2007	1.0	2.8
Q1		
2007	0.7	2.6
Q2		
2007	0.8	2.0
Q3		

2007	0.7	2.3
Q4		
2008	0.5	2.5
Q1		
2008	-0.5	3.3
Q2		
2008	-1.5	4.5
Q3		
2008	-2.2	3.7
Q4		
2009	-1.9	2.9
Q1		
2009	-0.3	2.0
Q2		
2009	0.1	1.4
Q3		
2009	0.3	1.6
Q4		
2010	0.9	2.4
Q1		
2010	1.1	2.5
Q2		

2010	0.6	2.3
Q3		
2010	0.1	2.7
Q4		
2011	0.3	3.5
Q1		
2011	0.1	3.8
Q2		
2011	0.2	4.0
Q3		
2011	0.0	4.0
Q4		
2012	0.8	3.1
Q1		
2012	-0.1	2.5
Q2		
2012	1.2	2.2
Q3		
2012	-0.1	2.4
Q4		
2013	0.2	2.5
Q1		

2013	0.7	2.4
Q2		
2013	0.7	2.4
Q3		
2013	0.6	1.9
Q4		
2014	0.9	1.6
Q1		
2014	0.9	1.6
Q2		
2014	0.8	1.5
Q3		
2014	0.7	1.1
Q4		
2015	0.4	0.4
Q1		
2015	0.6	0.3
Q2		
2015	0.4	0.4
Q3		
2015	0.7	0.4
Q4		

2016	0.4	0.7
Q1		
2016	0.6	0.7
Q2		
2016	0.4	1.0
Q3		
2016	0.6	1.5
Q4		
2017	0.7	2.2
Q1		
2017	0.5	2.6
Q2		
2017	0.5	2.7
Q3		
2017	0.6	2.8
Q4		
2018	0.1	2.5
Q1		
2018	0.5	2.2
Q2		
2018	0.6	2.3
Q3		

2018	0.3	2.1
Q4		
2019	0.6	1.8
Q1		
2019	0.1	2.0
Q2		
2019	0.6	1.8
Q3		
2019	0.0	1.4
Q4		
2020	-2.6	1.7
Q1		
2020	-21.0	0.8
Q2		
2020	16.6	0.8
Q3		
2020	1.2	0.8
Q4		
2021	-1.1	0.9
Q1		
2021	6.5	2.1
Q2		

2021 Q3	1.7	2.7
2021 Q4	1.5	4.4
2022 Q1	0.5	5.5
2022 Q2	0.1	7.9
2022 Q3	-0.1	8.7
2022 Q4	0.1	9.4
2023 Q1	0.1	9.0

Correlation Analysis

	A	B	C	D
1		<i>UK GDP (%)</i>	<i>UK Consumer Price Inflation (%)</i>	
2	UK GDP (%)	1		
3	UK Consumer Price Inflation (%)	-0.025831934	1	
4				
5				

Regression Analysis

UK GDP vs. Inflation 32

1	SUMMARY OUTPUT								
2									
3	Regression Statistics								
4	Multiple R	0.025832							
5	R Square	0.000667							
6	Adjusted R Square	-0.01198							
7	Standard Error	1.763142							
8	Observations	81							
9									
10	ANOVA								
11		<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
12	Regression	1	0.163985	0.163985	0.052751	0.818937			
13	Residual	79	245.5849	3.10867					
14	Total	80	245.7489						
15									
16		<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
17	Intercept	2.442403	0.197293	12.37959	3.47E-20	2.049701	2.835104	2.049701	2.835104
18	UK GDP (%)	-0.01434	0.062454	-0.22968	0.818937	-0.13866	0.109967	-0.13866	0.109967
19									
20									
21									
22	RESIDUAL OUTPUT								